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Behind closed doors: Homeboundness and psychosocial outcomes. Evidence from a longitudinal study of middle-aged and older adults

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Examine how homeboundness is associated with psychosocial outcomes.
- Longitudinal data from a nationally representative sample was used.
- Onset of homeboundness contributes to unfavorable psychosocial outcomes.
- Efforts to avoid homeboundness may assist in ageing successfully.

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ABSTRACT

Objectives: To examine how homeboundness is associated with psychosocial outcomes in terms of life satisfaction, positive affect, negative affect and loneliness among middle-aged and older adults.

Methods: Longitudinal data were taken from the nationally representative sample German Ageing Survey (wave 1 to wave 4; $n = 18,491$ observations). This study included community-dwelling individuals aged 40 years and over in Germany. The mean age in the analytic sample was 62.3 years (SD: 11.8 years). Established tools were used to quantify the psychosocial outcomes. Spending six or more days per week at home was defined as homeboundness. It was adjusted for several time-varying covariates. An asymmetric linear FE regression model with cluster-robust standard errors was applied.

Results: There was a robust association between the onset of homeboundness and an increase in loneliness. Among individuals aged 40 to 64 years, the onset of homeboundness was significantly associated with decreases in positive affect, whereas the end of homeboundness was significantly associated with decreases in negative affect. In contrast, changes in homeboundness status were not significantly associated with changes in psychosocial outcomes among individuals aged 65 years and over.

Conclusion: The onset of homeboundness in particular can contribute to unfavorable psychosocial outcomes, particularly in terms of increases in loneliness. Efforts to avoid homeboundness may assist in ageing successfully.

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1. Introduction

Homeboundness refers to a state in which an individual is unable to leave or rarely leaves their home. Reasons can vary from health-related factors (e.g., functional impairment, injuries or chronic conditions) to psychological reasons (e.g., fear of crime or stigmatisation). According to a former study from France, the number of individuals being homebound was nearly 5 % among community-dwelling individuals aged 65 years and over (Herr et al., 2013) (see also: (Hajek et al., 2024)). Some studies have examined the consequences of being homebound. Well-explored consequences of being homebound are poor mental and physical health (Qiu et al., 2010) and a higher mortality risk (Herr et al., 2013).

However, thus far, only some studies have explored how being homebound is associated with psychosocial factors (in terms of subjective well-being and loneliness). Subjective well-being refers to both affective well-being (i.e., positive and negative affect) as well as cognitive well-being (i.e., life satisfaction). Loneliness refers to a perceived discrepancy between desired and actual social relationships, either quantitatively or qualitatively. In fact, most of the existing studies in this research area are somewhat restricted by the fact that they rely on cross-sectional data (Ko & Noh, 2021). Such findings may be distorted by unobserved factors (e.g., genetic factors which are often unavailable) (Cameron & Trivedi, 2005). Moreover, it is difficult to draw causal conclusions based on the existing evidence. Longitudinal studies are thus required. For example, a recent longitudinal study showed that becoming homebound was associated with a reduction in life satisfaction after traumatic brain injury (de Souza et al., 2024). Other studies also focused on the link between home confinement during Covid-19 lockdown with subsequent well-being outcomes. For example, a study by Shiba et al. (2024) showed that this home confinement during the pandemic was associated with lower life satisfaction and greater loneliness. In summary, however, there is limited knowledge on the association between homeboundness and psychosocial outcomes in the older general population based on longitudinal data.

Due to this restricted knowledge, our aim was to examine the association between being homebound and psychosocial outcomes (in terms of life satisfaction, positive affect, negative affect and loneliness) using a longitudinal approach based on a nationally representative sample of middle-aged and older adults. In this study, we investigate both the beginning and the end of homeboundness in association with psychosocial outcomes. We assume that the onset of homeboundness in particular is significantly associated with psychosocial outcomes due to the fact that, in general, the effects of bad events are often more severe than those of good events (Baumeister et al., 2001). The knowledge of this study may assist in getting a better understanding of the associations between such factors. It may help to characterize individuals at risk of unfavourable psychosocial outcomes. This in turn may help individuals to age successfully.

2. Methods

2.1. Sample

Data were obtained from waves 1 (year 1996), 2 (2002), 3 (2008), and 4 (2011) of the German Ageing Survey (DEAS). We used data from these four waves for data availability reasons. The DEAS study is funded by the Federal Ministry for Family Affairs, Senior Citizens, Women, and Youth (BMFSFJ). It includes individuals aged 40 years and over living in private households. The DEAS study follows a cohort-sequential design, introducing new baseline samples mainly every six years (specifically in wave 2, wave 3), while panel assessments were conducted in wave 4. This means that only those individuals were included in wave 4 who already participated before.

Numerous topics were included in the DEAS study such as perception of old age, issues related to labor force, marital situation, psychosocial

factors or health in general. Individuals are first interviewed in the DEAS study. The interview covers, among other things, sociodemographic factors. More sensitive topics such as psychosocial issues were included in the additional self-completed questionnaire. The questionnaire was handed to participants after the interview. This questionnaire is available for around 83 % of all individuals being interviewed.

The DEAS study followed the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki. Notably, the study did not need an ethics vote as the conditions for such a requirement were not fulfilled (risks to respondents, lack of transparency regarding the aims of this study, examination of patients).

2.2. Dependent variables

Life satisfaction, positive affect, negative affect and loneliness were used as outcomes. Life satisfaction was quantified using the Satisfaction with Life Scale (SWLS) (Pavot & Diener, 1993). It refers to the cognitive evaluation of the whole life. The SWLS has five items. All items were averaged to build a final score. This score varies from 1 to 5, with higher values reflecting greater life satisfaction. In wave 4, for example, Cronbach's alpha was 0.84 (McDonald's omega: 0.85).

The positive affect and negative affect schedule (PANAS) (Watson et al., 1988) was used to measure positive and negative affect. Each of the positive and negative affect subscales is comprised of ten items. The final scores for both subscales were calculated as the mean of the ten items. The final scores both range from 1 to 5, whereby higher values reflect greater positive or negative affect, respectively. The Cronbach's alpha values for the positive and negative affect subscales were 0.85 and 0.86 (McDonald's omega was 0.86 for both PA and NA) respectively in wave 4.

Loneliness was quantified using the De Jong Gierveld tool, which consists of six items (Gierveld & Tilburg, 2006). One item, for example, is: "I miss the pleasure of the company of others". By averaging all six items, a final score was computed. This final score ranges from 1 to 4, whereby higher scores reflect higher loneliness scores. For example, in wave 4, Cronbach's alpha was 0.81 (McDonald's omega: 0.82).

2.3. Independent variable of interest: homeboundness

Time spent at home was used to quantify homeboundness. To this end, individuals were asked: "And how many days per week are you at home all day - apart from brief outings to do the shopping or go for walks?" in days. Following previous research (Ko & Noh, 2021), we dichotomized it into: absence of homeboundness (< 6 days per week) and presence of homeboundness (6 or more days per week).

2.4. Time-varying covariates

Guided by previous research (Hajek et al., 2023; Ko & Noh, 2021), several sociodemographic, lifestyle-related and health-related time-varying covariates were included. Sociodemographic covariates include age, family status (five categories: widowed; single; divorced; married, living separated from spouse; married, living together with spouse), and employment status (three categories: employed; retired; other: not employed). It was also adjusted for the lifestyle-related covariate frequency of sports activity (six categories; from 1 = "never" to 6 = "daily"). Furthermore, it was adjusted for the health-related covariates self-rated health (single-item measure from 1 = "very good" to 5 = "very bad") and number of chronic conditions (based on the presence of eleven chronic conditions; for example, diabetes or cancer).

Of note, to describe the sample, the time-constant sociodemographic factors sex (men; women) and education (ISCED-97 classification (UNESCO, 2006): low, medium or high education) were used.

In sensitivity analysis, it was also adjusted for the number of important people in regular contact (0 to 9) and providing instrumental support (no or yes).

In further sensitivity analysis, it was additionally adjusted for the

time-varying health-related covariates depressive symptoms (based on the CES-D (Radloff, 1977), 15-item version; from 0 to 45, whereby higher values reflect more depressive symptoms) and physical functioning (based on the physical functioning subscale of the SF-36 (Ware & Sherbourne, 1992); from 0 to 100, whereby higher values reflect better physical functioning). Such factors were only included in a sensitivity analysis because they were introduced from wave 2 onwards (and not from wave 1). In a last sensitivity analysis, it was also adjusted for informal caregiving (no or yes).

2.5. Statistical analysis

First, sample characteristics for the analytical sample are depicted. Subsequently, asymmetric linear fixed effects (FE) regressions (Allison, 2019) were estimated to explore the longitudinal association between homeboundness and the psychosocial outcomes (also stratified by age group: 40 to 64 years; 65 years and over). It was adjusted for time-varying factors listed in the section before.

A well-known key advantage of FE regressions is their ability to produce consistent estimates even under quite weak assumptions. For instance, FE regressions produce consistent estimates even in scenarios where time-invariant factors - whether observable or not - are correlated with the explanatory variables. This is in contrast to random-effects regressions, which would yield inconsistent estimates under such conditions (Cameron & Trivedi, 2005). Our choice of using FE regressions (compared to RE regressions) is substantiated by a series of Hausman-tests with cluster-robust standard errors (e.g., Sargan-Hansen statistic was 127.67, $p < .001$ when life satisfaction served as outcome among the total sample). FE regressions focus solely on variations within individuals over time (e.g., intraindividual changes in homeboundness status from wave 1 to wave 4). For example, one can analyze how the onset and the end of homeboundness is associated with loneliness levels within the same individuals during the course of these four waves. Consequently, only time-varying variables can serve as the main explanatory factors in FE regressions. Time-invariant variables, such as sex, cannot function as main effects. However, such time-invariant factors (both, observed and unobserved) are implicitly controlled when using a FE-framework. This emphasis on participants who experienced changes in both independent and dependent variables is not a drawback of the FE strategy; rather, it highlights that only a part of the population actually experiences such changes over time.

Of note that conventional FE models assume that variables have symmetric effects (e.g., the association between the onset of homeboundness and psychosocial outcomes is the same as the association between the end of homeboundness and psychosocial outcomes in absolute terms). Nevertheless, we assume that asymmetric effects may be more reasonable since bad events (here: the onset of homeboundness) often have stronger effects than good events (here: the end of homeboundness) (Baumeister et al., 2001). Thus, we used asymmetric linear FE regressions in this study. Cluster-robust standard errors were calculated (Stock & Watson, 2008).

McDonald's omega was calculated using a recently developed tool (Shaw, 2021). Statistical significance was defined by a p-value of <0.05 . The statistical analyses were performed using StataNow 18.5 (Stata Corp., College Station, Texas).

3. Results

3.1. Sample characteristics

The pooled analytic sample ($n = 18,491$ observations) is described in Table 1. The average age equaled 62.3 years (SD: 11.8 years; from 40 to 95 years) and 49.0 % were female. Average life satisfaction was 3.7 (SD: 1.2), average positive affect was 3.3 (SD: 1.4), average negative affect was 1.9 (SD: 1.3) and average loneliness was 1.7 (SD: 1.0). More details are shown in Table 1. Of note that 519 participants changed to

Table 1
Sample characteristics (analytic sample with $n = 18,491$ observations, pooled).

Variables	Mean (SD) / n (%)
Age	62.3 (11.8)
Sex	
Men	9437 (51.0)
Women	9054 (49.0)
Marital status	
Married, living together with spouse	13,465 (72.8)
Married, living separated from spouse	262 (1.4)
Divorced	1443 (7.8)
Widowed	2321 (12.6)
Single	1000 (5.4)
Education (ISCED-classification)	
Low	2190 (11.9)
Medium	10,020 (54.2)
High	6271 (33.9)
Employment status	
Employed	6674 (36.1)
Retired	9186 (49.7)
Other: not employed	2631 (14.2)
Frequency of sports activities	
Daily	1299 (7.0)
Several times a week	3535 (19.1)
Once a week	3079 (16.7)
1-3 times per month	1449 (7.8)
Less often	2171 (11.7)
Never	6958 (37.6)
Self-rated health (1 = "very good" to 5 = "very bad")	2.5 (0.8)
Number of chronic conditions (from 0 to 11)	2.4 (1.9)
Life satisfaction (from 1 to 5, with higher values reflecting greater life satisfaction)	3.7 (1.2)
Positive affect (from 1 to 5, with higher values reflecting greater positive affect)	3.3 (1.4)
Negative affect (from 1 to 5, with higher values reflecting greater negative affect)	1.9 (1.3)
Loneliness (from 1 to 4, with higher values reflecting greater loneliness)	1.7 (1.0)

homeboundness from wave 1 to wave 4, whereas 466 participants changed to the absence of homeboundness in this period.

3.2. Regression analysis

Findings of asymmetric linear FE regressions are shown in Table 2 (among the total sample) and in Table 3 (stratified by age group). Among the total sample, the onset of homeboundness was significantly associated with an increase in negative affect ($\beta = 0.14, p < .05$) and loneliness ($\beta = 0.09, p < .05$), whereas it was not significantly associated

Table 2
Homeboundness and psychosocial outcomes among the total sample. Results of asymmetric linear FE regressions (wave 1 to wave 4).

	Life satisfaction	Positive affect	Negative affect	Loneliness
Onset of homeboundness	-0.01 (0.06)	0.09 (0.07)	0.14* (0.06)	0.09* (0.04)
End of homeboundness	-0.05 (0.05)	-0.05 (0.05)	-0.06 (0.06)	0.03 (0.05)
Time-varying covariates †	✓	✓	✓	✓
Observations	18,489	18,491	18,491	18,467
Individuals	12,198	12,200	12,200	12,195
R ²	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.01

Comments: Unstandardized beta coefficients are presented. Cluster-robust standard errors are shown in parentheses. *** $p < .001$, ** $p < .01$, * $p < .05$, + $p < .10$. † Time-varying covariates include age, marital status, employment status, frequency of sports activities, self-rated health and number of chronic conditions.

Table 3

Homeboundness and psychosocial outcomes stratified by age group. Results of asymmetric linear FE regressions (wave 1 to wave 4).

	Life satisfaction among individuals aged 40 to 64 years	Positive affect among individuals aged 40 to 64 years	Negative affect among individuals aged 40 to 64 years	Loneliness among individuals aged 40 to 64 years	Life satisfaction among individuals aged 65 years and over	Positive affect among individuals aged 65 years and over	Negative affect among individuals aged 65 years and over	Loneliness among individuals aged 65 years and over
Onset of homeboundness	0.08 (0.09)	-0.09* (0.04)	0.02 (0.07)	0.10* (0.05)	-0.05 (0.09)	0.11 (0.11)	0.15 (0.11)	0.17+ (0.09)
End of homeboundness	-0.09 (0.09)	-0.13+ (0.07)	-0.18* (0.08)	0.08 (0.08)	-0.01 (0.07)	-0.02 (0.09)	0.01 (0.10)	0.01 (0.10)
Time-varying covariates†	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Observations	10,311	10,313	10,313	10,304	8178	8178	8178	8163
Individuals	7241	7241	7241	7237	5930	5933	5933	5925
R ²	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.01

Unstandardized beta coefficients are presented. Cluster-robust standard errors are shown in parentheses. *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$, + $p < 0.10$. † Time-varying covariates include age, marital status, employment status, frequency of sports activities, self-rated health and number of chronic conditions.

with changes in life satisfaction and positive affect. The end of homeboundness was not significantly associated with changes in the psychosocial outcomes among the total sample. Such aforementioned results remained the same in terms of effect size when it was also adjusted for providing instrumental support and the number of important people in regular contact in a sensitivity analysis. With regard to time-varying covariates, it is worth noting that only increases in chronic conditions were consistently significantly associated with unfavorable psychosocial outcomes (i.e., decreases in life satisfaction and positive affect as well as increases in negative affect and loneliness).

Stratified by age group, the onset of homeboundness was (mainly) consistently associated with an increase in loneliness (among individuals 40 to 64 years: $\beta = 0.10$, $p < .05$; marginal significance among individuals 65 years and over: $\beta = 0.17$, $p = .054$). Moreover, it was significantly associated with a decrease in positive affect ($\beta = -0.09$, $p < .05$) among individuals aged 40 to 64 years. The end of homeboundness was significantly associated with a decrease in negative affect ($\beta = -0.18$, $p < .05$) in this age group. Changes in homeboundness status were not significantly associated with changes in psychosocial outcomes among individuals aged 65 years and over. When we take an even deeper look (based on age quartiles), the onset of homeboundness was particularly significantly associated with decreases in positive affect ($\beta = -0.16$, $p < .05$) and increases in loneliness ($\beta = 0.17$, $p < .05$) among the second age quartile.

In a robustness check (see Supplementary Table 1), it was additionally adjusted for depressive symptoms and physical functioning (and informal caregiving). Of note and worth repeating that data were used from wave 2 to wave 4 in this robustness check since these variables were introduced in the second wave. Compared to the main model (presented in Table 2), there was also an association between the onset of homeboundness and an increase in loneliness ($\beta = 0.11$, $p < .05$) among the total sample. However, while the significant association between the onset of homeboundness and increases in negative affect vanished, the association between the end of homeboundness and a decrease in negative affect gained statistical significance ($\beta = -0.12$, $p < .01$). When informal caregiving was added as additional time-varying covariate, the findings remained virtually the same (see Supplementary Table 1).

4. Discussion

Using data from a large, representative sample, our aim was to investigate the association between homeboundness and psychosocial outcomes among middle-aged and older adults based on a longitudinal approach. Our key findings: There was a robust association between the onset of homeboundness and an increase in loneliness. Among

individuals aged 40 to 64 years, the onset of homeboundness was significantly associated with decreases in positive affect, whereas the end of homeboundness was significantly associated with decreases in negative affect. In contrast, changes in homeboundness status were not significantly associated with changes in psychosocial outcomes among individuals aged 65 years and over. Based on longitudinal data of a population-based sample of middle-aged and older adults, our study markedly extends our current understanding in this research area mainly based on cross-sectional studies (Ko & Noh, 2021).

Several factors may explain the association between the onset of homeboundness and increases in loneliness. An obvious reason is that individuals being homebound may have restricted social interactions (e.g., with friends) which in turn may foster feelings of exclusion and loneliness. Furthermore, homeboundness may disrupt daily routines involving social interaction. This loss of routine may foster feelings of loneliness. Additionally, individuals being homebound may also have fewer opportunities to participate in social activities or community events. They may lose contact with their social environment in general. The quality of contacts could also decrease over time when being homebound. For example, only rather unavoidable contacts with, for example, postmen, craftsmen, carers, physicians might be maintained. Such contacts probably cannot compensate for important missing high-quality social relationships (Hawkey et al., 2008; Kristensen et al., 2019). The marginal significant association ($p = .054$) between becoming homebound and increases in loneliness among older adults may be explained by a lack of statistical power.

Of note that based on the range of the loneliness outcome, the changes identified in this study (in terms of beta-coefficients) were mostly moderate. Nonetheless, the results underscore the significance of homeboundness in shaping loneliness scores. For example, the beta-coefficient for the homeboundness-loneliness association identified in our study was more than twice as large as the beta-coefficient for the association of an increase in one chronic condition with loneliness. Among individuals aged 40 to 64 years, the onset of homeboundness was associated with decreases in positive affect, whereas the end of homeboundness was associated with decreases in negative affect. Changes in homeboundness status were not significantly associated with changes in psychosocial outcomes among individuals aged 65 years and over. This may be attributed to the fact that the reasons for being homebound may somewhat vary between individuals aged 40 to 64 years and individuals aged 65 years and over. Furthermore, among older adults in particular, becoming homebound may be perceived as a natural course of life and may therefore has less serious consequences, whereas middle-aged individuals may have various obligations (e.g., work, raising children, caregiving responsibilities) (Oh et al., 2020) that may keep them at home involuntarily. This may reduce positive

emotions among middle-aged individuals. Furthermore, they may compare with younger or older age groups (Hajek & König, 2024) that commonly have much more leisure time. Such negative comparisons may also decrease positive emotions (Hajek & König, 2016; 2019). Similarly, the end of being homebound could be a kind of liberation for middle-aged individuals. This may explain the significant association between the end of homeboundness and decreases in negative affect in this age group. However, it may be restricted to the area of negative affect. It is possible that individuals may find it difficult to reactivate old contacts or make new ones after the end of homeboundness, for example to reduce loneliness. However, we strongly recommend future research to explore the underlying mechanisms for such findings.

Several strengths and limitations are worth mentioning when interpreting the findings of this present study. Data were used from a large, nationally representative sample of middle-aged and older adults. Additionally, individuals were observed over a long period of time. Moreover, the challenge of unobserved heterogeneity was reduced by using FE regressions. Our current study also distinguished between the onset and the end of homeboundness. Very established and psychometrically sound tools were used to quantify all outcomes. It was adjusted for a wide array of covariates. In accordance with numerous previous studies (Ko & Noh, 2021), the time spent at home was used to quantify homeboundness. However, this may not fully capture the phenomenon of homeboundness. For example, the item used did not distinguish between voluntary activities such as reading a good book in peace and quiet and involuntary activities inside the home e.g., due to mobility restrictions or due to family obligations such as caring for close relatives. This is important in terms of personal preferences as opposed to external constraints. However, we strongly assume that this widely used tool is at least a good way proxy for the phenomenon of being homebound. Of note that only a small selection bias was found in the DEAS study.

5. Conclusion

In Germany, about one in five community-dwelling individuals aged 40 years and over can be classified as homebound. The onset of homeboundness, in particular, can contribute to unfavorable psychosocial outcomes, particularly in terms of increases in loneliness. Homeboundness represents a challenge that cannot be ignored. Efforts to avoid homeboundness may assist in ageing successfully. Upcoming research, particularly based on longitudinal data, is recommended. Moreover, the underlying mechanisms (e.g., decreases in social activities, diminished general self-esteem or other psychological factors) should be further explored in upcoming research.

Institutional review board statement

The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki. An ethical statement for the DEAS study was not necessary because criteria for the need of an ethical statement were not met (risk for the respondents, lack of information about the aims of the study, examination of patients). The German Centre of Gerontology, who is responsible for the DEAS study, did not apply for an ethics vote, based on the recommendation of a standing council of the DEAS that decided no ethics vote to be necessary.

Informed consent statement

Written informed consent was obtained from all subjects involved in the study.

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Data availability statement

The data used in this study are third-party data. The anonymized data sets of the DEAS (1996, 2002, 2008, 2011, 2014, 2017, 2020, 2020/2021) are available for secondary analysis. The data has been made available to scientists at universities and research institutes exclusively for scientific purposes. The use of data is subject to written data protection agreements. Microdata of the German Ageing Survey (DEAS) are available free of charge to scientific researchers for non-profitable purposes. The FDZ-DZA provides access and support to scholars interested in using DEAS for their research. However, for reasons of data protection, signing a data distribution contract is required before data can be obtained. For further information on the data distribution contract, please see <https://www.dza.de/en/research/fdz/access-to-data/application> (accessed on 20 January 2025).

CRediT authorship contribution statement

André Hajek: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Pinar Soysal:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Conceptualization. **Razak M. Gyasi:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Conceptualization. **Karel Kostev:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Conceptualization. **Supa Pengpid:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Conceptualization. **Karl Peltzer:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Conceptualization. **Hans-Helmut König:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Supervision, Resources, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [doi:10.1016/j.archger.2025.105767](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.archger.2025.105767).

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